

Encoder-decoder approach for describing health of cauliflower plant in multiple languages

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ABSTRACT

Physically examining each plant to determine its state of health and determining the disease if plant is affected due to it, is challenging. The encoder - decoder approach is proposed for describing health of cauliflower plant in English, Hindi, and Marathi languages from aerial images. Experiments are performed with different convolutional neural network (CNN) models and long short-term memory (LSTM) combinations. The multilanguage cauliflower captions dataset (MCCD) is developed to evaluate the performance of the model. The dataset contains 1213 images where each image is described in 3 different languages. The dataset contains images of cauliflower plant affected due to bacterial spot rot, black rot, and downy mildew diseases. It also contains images of healthy plant. The objective metrics such as bilingual evaluation understudy (BLEU) scores and subjective criteria are used to decide the quality of the generated description.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The manual methods of crop monitoring are labour intensive, time consuming and may results in grossly inaccurate estimates. By automating the process of monitoring of crop health these challenges can be addressed. This paper proposes automation of crop monitoring process. The encoder-decoder approach is proposed for describing health of cauliflower plant in English, Hindi, and Marathi languages. The aerial images of farmland can be taken using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). Later, these images will be analysed by machine learning algorithm to describe health of the crop using captions in multiple languages.

The Hindi language is official language of Government of India and among top 5 globally spoken languages [1]. The third most widely spoken language in India is Marathi, which is also the official language of the state of Maharashtra [2]. Cauliflower is a member of the cruciferous family and has nutritional value. It contains vitamins, nutrients, fiber, and antioxidants [3], [4]. The Figure 1 shows the global production/yield quantities of cauliflowers and broccoli from year 1994 to 2020 [5].

The Figure 2 shows top cauliflower and broccoli producing countries during 1994 to 2021 [5]. During this period India was its second largest producer. The cauliflower plant is commonly affected by bacterial spot rot, black rot, and downy mildew diseases. Previously, researchers concentrated primarily on recognizing cauliflower disease from images [6]–[10] and did not explore generating descriptions about its health from aerial images in many languages. Three types of methodologies are utilized in the process of generating descriptions: encoder-decoder approaches [11]–[16], picture retrieval [17], and object recognition

[18]. In comparison to other approaches, the encoder-decoder approach produced superior results [19]. As a result, an encoder-decoder approach is proposed here for generating descriptions in multiple languages.

Figure 1. Global production/yield quantities of cauliflowers and broccoli [5]

Figure 2. Top Cauliflower and broccoli producing countries [5]

2. PROPOSED ENCODER-DECODER APPROACH

The suggested encoder-decoder method for using an aerial image to express the health of a cauliflower plant in several languages is depicted in Figure 3. The images of farmland will be captured using UAV such as a drone. These images will act as in input to the encoder block.

Figure 3. Proposed methodology for explaining health of cauliflower plant in multiple languages

Using aerial image of cauliflower fields as input, convolutional neural network (CNN) acts as an encoder in the model, extracting features from them. To prevent losing spatial information, the output of the CNN model's pooling layer is used instead of the last fully linked layer. The decoder is given the CNN-generated features as well as their descriptions. However, in the suggested method, the long short-term memory (LSTM) network serves as a decoder since it overcomes the recurrent neural networks (RNN) declining gradient problem [20].

During the training phase, the decoder learns how to provide a description of an image using its characteristics and previously produced words. In this method, each word is given a probability depending on its distinguishing characteristics and the preceding word. Figure 4 depicts the flowchart of proposed encoder-

decoder approach. The same approach is followed to generate captions in other languages because we transform words to numbers in step 8 of the flowchart.

Experiments on feature extraction were carried out using several pre-trained CNN architectures, including visual geometry group 16 (VGG-16) [21], InceptionResNetV2 [22], and EfficientNetV2L [23]. The top-1 accuracy of VGG-16, InceptionResNetV2 and EfficientNetV2L CNN model is 71.30%, 80.30% and 85.70% respectively on ImageNet validation dataset [24]. The top-1 accuracy of the model indicates that the predicted label matches the target label. The top-5 accuracy of VGG-16, InceptionResNetV2, and EfficientNetV2L CNN model is 90.10%, 95.30%, and 97.50% respectively on ImageNet validation dataset [24]. The top-5 accuracy of the model indicates that the target label is one among the top 5 predicted label.

The VGG-16 is a CNN architecture that stands for VGG-16. VGG-16 is known for its depth because to its 16 layers, which include 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully linked layers. The design is made up of smaller 3×3 convolutional filters layered on top of each other, allowing for more detailed aspects of the input image to be captured. It employs a straightforward and consistent design paradigm in which convolutional layers are followed by max-pooling layers to lower spatial dimensions. The ImageNet dataset was used to train the VGG-16 model, which comprises millions of labelled images from diverse object categories.

A combination of the Inception and ResNet models is the InceptionResNetV2 model. The Inception architecture, upon which the InceptionResNetV2 model is based, combines convolutional layers with varying kernel sizes to collect information at various scales. EfficientNetV2L is an EfficientNet model family CNN model. The "V2L" in EfficientNetV2L stands for "vision to language". This model was created especially for multimodal activities that need the processing of textual and visual data.

Figure 4. Flowchart for proposed approach

3. DATASET

The multilanguage cauliflower captions dataset (MCCD) is developed to evaluate the proposed model's performance. The dataset comprises 1213 colour images, each of which is accompanied by a caption written in English, Hindi, and Marathi language. The 656 images were captured in Bangladesh and provided in [25]. The remaining 557 images were obtained by the authors in 2023 on farmland in the Nashik district of Maharashtra State, India using a drone. The composition of the MCCD is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of MCCD

Category	Number of images		
	Images from Bangladesh [25]	Images captured in India	Total images
Bacterial spot rot	173	126	299
Black rot	100	158	258
Downy mildew	177	106	283
No disease/healthy plant	206	167	373
Total	656	557	1213

An agronomist captions each image with information in Marathi, Hindi, and English on the health of the cauliflower plant. Thus, there are 1213 captions in the dataset in Marathi, Hindi, and English. The dataset includes images of cauliflower plants infected by various diseases such as bacterial spot rot, black rot, and downy mildew, as well as images of healthy plants. The images were acquired from many sources and in various weather conditions, resulting in a diversified collection.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Evaluation on objective metrics

The resulting caption quality of the proposed approach is validated using quantitative metrics bilingual evaluation understudy (BLEU). The BLEU metric is established in [26], and it uses a weighted average to compare various length phrase matches to the reference sentence. It counts the number of times an n-gram appears in the produced caption and the dataset's reference caption, where an n-gram is a collection of one or more ordered words. The BLEU is a precision-based score that ranges from 0 to 1, with a higher value suggesting a better match. For calculation of the score, the brevity penalty (BP) is calculated as (1):

$$BP = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } c > r \\ e^{(1-\frac{r}{c})}, & \text{if } c \ll r \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where, c is the length of the generated caption and r is the reference caption length. The BLEU score is computed as (2):

$$BLEU = BP \cdot \exp(\sum_{n=1}^N w_n \log p_n) \quad (2)$$

Where, p_n is modified n-gram precision, N is n-gram length, w_n is the positive weights and the sum of w_n is one.

For various N values, the BLEU number is computed. BLEU-1 makes use of a unigram precision value, but BLEU-2 makes use of a geometric sum of unigram and bigram precision. The BLEU-3 uses the geometric average of unigram, bigram, and trigram accuracy, whereas the BLEU-4 uses the geometric average of unigram, bigram, trigram, and four-gram precision. The Table 2 presents the BLEU metrics for several CNN models. From VGG-16 through InceptionResNetV2 to EfficientNetV2L, the quality of caption improves on all four BLEU measures. The BLEU score achieved for captions generated in multiple languages for specific model is also comparable.

Table 2. Results on objective metrics

CNN model	Language of caption	BLEU-1	BLEU-2	BLEU-3	BLEU-4
VGG-16	English	0.79	0.76	0.73	0.69
	Hindi	0.78	0.74	0.72	0.69
	Marathi	0.78	0.75	0.73	0.68
InceptionResNetV2	English	0.86	0.81	0.77	0.74
	Hindi	0.86	0.82	0.77	0.73
	Marathi	0.85	0.81	0.76	0.72
EfficientNetV2L	English	0.90	0.84	0.80	0.77
	Hindi	0.90	0.83	0.79	0.75
	Marathi	0.89	0.82	0.80	0.75

4.2. Evaluation on subjective criteria

To determine the quality of the caption, the BLEU score just contrasts the generated caption with the reference captions. An objective agronomist thoroughly verifies the generated description in subjective judgement. Three categories—correct, partially correct, and incorrect—are created from the generated caption and are based on quality. The findings on subjective criteria for several CNN models are displayed in Table 3. Overall, caption quality is better from VGG-16 to InceptionResNetV2 to EfficientNetV2L.

Figure 5 compares the performance of several CNN models based on subjective criteria. Similar to objective assessments, the performance of various models for numerous languages is similar. The InceptionResNetV2 and EfficientNetV2L models beat the VGG-16 model, which is deemed shallow because to its low number of layers.

The Figure 6 shows results for EfficientNetV2L CNN model while Figure 7 shows the results for InceptionResNetV2 CNN model. The Figure 6 contains test image of cauliflower plant which is affected due to bacterial spot rot disease. The Figure 7 contains test image of cauliflower plant which is in healthy condition.

If the generated description accurately portrays the health of the cauliflower plant with no grammatical errors, it falls into the correct category. The caption generated in both English and Hindi language for test image provided in Figure 6 is categorized as correct. Similarly, the caption generated in English language for test image shown in Figure 7 is also categorized in correct category. If the description is erroneous, linguistically faulty, or useless, it is placed in the incorrect category. The caption generated in Marathi language for test image provided in Figure 7 falls into this category as the generated caption is meaningless.

Table 3. Results on subjective criteria

CNN model	Language of caption	Correct caption (%)	Partially correct caption (%)	Incorrect caption (%)
VGG-16	English	77.00	15.11	7.89
	Hindi	76.08	15.13	8.79
	Marathi	76.03	14.09	9.88
InceptionResNetV2	English	84.19	11.03	4.78
	Hindi	85.16	8.87	5.97
	Marathi	83.97	10.11	5.92
EfficientNetV2L	English	87.60	10.81	1.59
	Hindi	86.97	11.94	1.09
	Marathi	86.97	11.02	2.01

Figure 5. Comparison of results on subjective criteria

Language	Reference caption	Generated caption	Category of generated caption
English	Bacterial spot rot has infected the head of a cauliflower plant.	Bacterial spot rot has infected the head of a cauliflower plant.	Correct
Hindi	फूलगोभी के फूल	फूलगोभी के फूल	Correct
	जीवाणु रोग से संक्रमित हो गए हैं।	जीवाणु रोग से संक्रमित हो गए हैं।	
Marathi	फुलकोबीच्या	फुलकोबीच्या	Partially correct
	फुलोऱ्याला जिवाणूजन्य	फुलोऱ्याला संसर्ग	
	आजाराचा संसर्ग झाला आहे.	झाला आहे.	

Figure 6. Results for EfficientNetV2L CNN model

Language	Reference caption	Generated caption	Category of generated caption
English	A healthy and fresh cauliflower crop is growing at a reasonable rate.	A healthy and fresh cauliflower crop is growing at a reasonable rate.	Correct
Hindi	ताजा और स्वस्थ फूलगोभी की फसल अच्छी गति से बढ़ रही है।	स्वस्थ फूलगोभी की फसल गति से बढ़ रही है।	Partially correct
Marathi	ताजे आणि निरोगी फुलकोबीचे पीक योग्य गतीने वाढत आहे.	ताजे पीक आहे.	Incorrect

Figure 7. Results for InceptionResNetV2 CNN model

A statement that accurately characterizes the plant's health but does not give specifics is classified as partially correct. The caption generated in Marathi language for test image provided in Figure 6 is categorized as partially correct as caption indicated that cauliflower plant is affected but fails to provide details of the disease. Similarly, the caption generated in Hindi language for test image shown in Figure 7 is also categorized in same category as it hides other details of healthy plant.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The encoder-decoder approach is proposed to generate captions in multiple languages to describe health of cauliflower plant from aerial images. The experiments are performed with CNN models such as VGG-16, InceptionResNetV2, EfficientNetV2L, and LSTM combinations. On both BLEU score and subjective criteria EfficientNetV2L-LSTM combination has provided superior results. The InceptionResNetV2 and EfficientNetV2L have performed substantially well than VGG-16 as they have more layers which results in better feature extraction. The captions generated in various languages were of comparable quality.

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